

FREQUENCY OF REFRACTIVE ERRORS IN DIFFERENT ABO BLOOD GROUPS AMONG PATIENTS VISITING UNIVERSITY OF LAHORE TEACHING HOSPITAL

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Abstract

Background: Refractive errors are the most common cause of visual impairment worldwide, affecting over 2.3 billion people and significantly impacting quality of life if left uncorrected. These errors, including myopia, hypermetropia, and astigmatism, arise due to improper focusing of light on the retina and are influenced by both genetic and environmental factors. The ABO blood group system, first discovered by Karl Landsteiner, represents one of the most significant genetic markers in human populations and has been linked with susceptibility to various diseases. Limited research has explored the possible association between refractive errors and ABO blood groups, suggesting that certain blood groups may predispose individuals to specific types of refractive errors. Given the scarcity of local studies, it is important to investigate whether any relationship exists between blood group distribution and refractive errors in patients visiting the University of Lahore Teaching Hospital (UOLTH).

Objective: Frequency of refractive errors in different ABO blood groups among patients visiting University of Lahore Teaching Hospital Lahore.

Methodology: A descriptive cross-sectional study of patients visiting eye department was carried out by evaluating frequency of refractive errors in different blood groups. Blood group of each patient has been checked. All patients from the age 17 to 35 years visiting the department with any type of refractive error and blood group included in the study irrespective of their sex.

Results: A total of 215 patients were assessed. 21 patients are astigmatism with frequency of 9.8 of all. 3 patients have AB+, 4 patients have A+, 7 have B+, 5 have O+, and 2 patients have O- blood groups. 25 patients are hyperopic and 11.5% is frequency of all. 6 patients have A+, 3 have AB+, 10 have B+ and 6 have O+ blood groups. 169 patients were myopic and 78.6% is frequency of all. 4 patients have A-, 26 have A+, 1 have AB-, 19 have AB+, 5 have B- blood group, 73 have B+ blood group, 3 have O- blood group and 3 have O+ blood groups. In case of left eye out of 215, 23 patients are astigmatic and frequency is 10.7% of

all. 3 patients have AB+, 4 patients have A+, 9 patients have B+, 5 patients have O+ and 2 patients have O- blood group. 25 patients are hyperopic and 11.6% is frequency of all. 6 patients have A+, 3 patients have AB+, 10 patients have B+ and 6 patients have O+ blood group. 167 patients are myopic and frequency is 77.7% of all. 4 patients have A-, 26 have A+, 1 patient has AB-, 19 have AB+, 5 patients have B-, 71 patients have B+, 3 patients have O- and 38 patients have O+ blood group.

Conclusion: This study concludes that highest frequency of refractive error is found among blood group B+, followed by blood group O+.

INTRODUCTION

Blood is the main liquid of life that helps to supply oxygen to all the organ of body and if does not exist, the working of human body will end up. Blood comprises of two main elements, serum and cells. The blood cells are made up from bone marrow. The blood serum of many people shows reaction to red blood cells of other person and this study arouse the recognition of ABO blood system. Because of reactions between RBC's and serum, Landsteiner classified it into four blood groups A, B, O and AB. Varieties of these blood groups are governed by the antigen present on RBC's surface. Blood group AB is universal recipient and O is universal donor (1).

Refractive errors are problems of the eye sight to focus light rays properly on the retina because change the shape of cornea and eye ball (2). Eye, having no refractive error when looking distant objects is said to be emmetropic eye, denoting the eye is in a state in which it can focus parallel rays of light from distant objects on the retina, without exerting any accommodation (3).

Myopia, hypermetropia and astigmatism are the different types of refractive error, among this myopia is the commonest (4). They are often categorized as spherical errors and cylindrical errors. Myopia is the refractive error in which parallel rays of light arriving from infinity fall in front of retina. Axial length of eye ball is increased in myopia, many factors lead to myopia including both controllable and uncontrollable factors such as Physical activities, diet and habits are included in controllable factors while age and genetics are uncontrollable factors (5,6,7).

In hypermetropia, the parallel rays of light fall behind the retina and the axial length of eye ball becomes shortened (8). This can arise from the crystalline lens or the cornea with not adequate curvature (refractive hyperopia) or the eyeball that is inordinately short

(axial hyperopia). Hyperopia can be rectified with convex lenses, which cause light rays to converge earlier to fall on the cornea. Astigmatism is an error of refraction due to rotational asymmetry in the refractive power of eye which results in distorted or blurred image at any distance (9).

Some refractive errors are more common in specified blood groups. By finding the highly frequent refractive error in specified blood group, we can limit the exposure of risk factors in the daily life routine of children and adults, so that they can get the refractive error late in life and in less severe form.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This cross-sectional study involved 50 patients aged 15-40 years of both genders to evaluate the association between ABO blood groups and refractive errors. The distribution of blood groups among patients was A (30%), B (32%), and O (38%). The Chi-square value was 0.4605 and p-value 0.79, indicating no statistically significant relationship between ABO blood groups and refractive errors. Myopia was more common in men, while hypermetropia was more frequent in women. The researchers concluded that blood group O showed slight predominance in myopia, but overall, no significant correlation existed between ABO blood groups and refractive errors. They also suggested that larger-scale studies are needed due to the small sample size and short study period (10).

A cross-sectional study conducted on 289 MBBS students aimed to determine the relationship between ABO blood groups and myopia. Out of all participants, 181 (62.6%) were myopic, with varying degrees of severity. The most prevalent blood groups were B+ (35%) and O+ (25%). Among myopic patients, O+ blood group showed the highest

prevalence and was found to have a statistically significant association with myopia ($p = 0.001$). The study concluded that individuals with blood group O have a higher risk of developing myopia compared to other groups. The authors emphasized that environmental and genetic factors both play roles in myopia development and that further research is needed to confirm these findings (11).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Cross-sectional study was conducted at University of Lahore Teaching Hospital between September 2022 to December 2022. After approval from IRB (institutional Review Board) and informed consent of patient, data was collected through a well-structured Performa. Subjects completing to 55 years with

according to refractive error. In 1st group, we took all myopic patients. In 2nd group we took all hyperopic patients and in 3rd group we took astigmatic patients. After performing all the procedure, we categorized patients of each group into further 4 sub-groups on the basis of blood type by using statistical approaches. Data was evaluated and analyzed with statistical software for social sciences (SPSS version 26.0).

RESULTS

Table 1: Blood Group in case of right eye.

In case of Right Eye, out of total 215 patients, 21 patients are Astigmatic. No body of these has A-, AB- and B- blood groups. 3 patients have AB+ blood group, 4 patients have A+ blood group, 7 patients have B+ blood group, 5 patients have O+ and 2

	Blood Group								Total
	A-	A+	AB-	AB+	B-	B+	O-	O+	
Astigmatic	0	4	0	3	0	7	2	5	21
Hyperopic	0	6	0	3	0	10	0	6	25
Myopic	4	26	1	19	5	73	3	38	169
Total	4	36	1	25	5	90	5	49	215

refractive error was selected by convenient random sampling. Patients having any other ocular and systemic diseases, blood dyscrasias and undergone through refractive surgery or IOL implantation were excluded from the study. 1st we evaluated the blood group of each patient of each group, by Haem agglutination rapid slide method using anti sera A, B and D. Haem agglutination was viewed on a glass slide that had been spillited into 3 parts where a drop of the donor's blood was added to each section. Anti A, anti B and anti D were added to one of the sections respectively to which agglutination occurred and blood type got determined. These haem agglutination Tests were performed at laboratories of UOLTH. After finding blood type, we did autorefractometer of each patient to find out baseline data then we took visual acuity of each patient, first at distance by using Snellen acuity chart at 6m. For this we seated each patient at 6 meter and asked him/her to read 6/60 line. If he could not read 6/60 then shifted to 5m distance and so on. Then we took VA at the near, by using Snellen near acuity chart at 33cm. After collecting data, patients were arranged in 3 groups

patients have O- blood group. Out of 215, 25 patients are Hyperopic. No patients of these have A-, AB-, B- and O- blood group. 6 patients have A+ blood group, 3 patients have AB+ blood group, 10 patients have B+ blood group and 6 patients has O+ blood group. Out of 215, 169 patients are Myopic. 4 patients have A- blood group, 26 patients have A+, 1 patient has AB-, 19 patients have AB+, 5 patients have B- blood group, 73 patients have B+ blood group, 3 patients have O- blood group and 38 patients have O+ blood group.

Table 2: Blood Group in case of left eye.

In case of Left Eye, Out of total 215 patients, 23 patients are Astigmatic. No body of these has A-, AB- and B- blood groups. 3 patients have AB+ blood group, 4 patients have A+ blood group, 9 patients have B+ blood group, 5 patients have O+ and 2 patients have O+ blood group.

Refractive Error	Blood group								Total
	A-	A+	AB-	AB+	B-	B+	O-	O+	
Astigmatic	0	4	0	3	0	9	2	5	23
Hyperopic	0	6	0	3	0	10	0	6	25
Myopic	4	26	1	19	5	71	3	38	167
Total	4	36	1	25	5	90	5	49	215

Out of 215, 25 patients are Hyperopic. No patients of these has A-, AB-, B- and O- blood group. 6 patients has A+ blood group, 3 patients has AB+ blood group, 10 patients has B+ blood group and 6 patients has O+ blood group.

Out of 215, 167 patients are Myopic. 4 patients have A- blood group, 26 patients have A+, 1 patient has AB-, 19 patients have AB+, 5 patients have B- blood group, 71 patients have B+ blood group, 3 patients have O- blood group and 38 patients have O+ blood group.

DISCUSSION

Total 215 number of patients age group 15-35 years of both genders were examined, having any type of refractive errors. In case of right eye, out of 215 patients, 169 patients are myopic, 25 patients were hypermetropic and 21 patients were Astigmatic. In case of Left Eye, out of total 215 patients, 167 patients were Myopic, 25 patients were hypermetropic and 23 patients were Astigmatic. Myopia was the most common refractive error and that was seen most commonly in blood group B+ followed by blood group O+ and least in blood group AB-. This study concludes that blood group B+ has highest frequency of myopia and AB- blood group has least frequency of refractive error. While blood group A+ has highest frequency of hypermetropia.

Sonal R, Gaonkar, Nalini Y C, et.al. analyze the distribution of ABO blood group and its relation to myopia, they used blood group as qualitative variable while refractive indices of myopia, hypermetropia and astigmatism as Quantitative variables. The findings of study revealed that there is 7.4 % blood group is AB+, 20 % blood group is A+ and 30 % blood group is O+. The most common blood group is B positive which consist 33%. Their results showed that the average age of the subjects was 18 years. In their study, myopia was highly pervasive in blood group B, followed by blood

group A, AB, and O (12). Alike results were also found by Seth et al 12 in Punjab, where blood group B predominated (35.84%), followed by blood groups A and O (both 24.52%) in myopia patients. Parallel findings from several antecedent researches revealed that blood group B occurs most frequently in myopic individuals confirm our findings in contrast, that blood type O subjects had higher incidence of myopia than those in other blood groups. Similar results have been achieved from the present study that blood group B+ is most frequent While most frequent refractive error in this blood group and age group is Myopia (13).

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that the highest frequency of refractive error is found among blood group B+, followed by blood group O+. For this study data was collected from a specific small population area that can be enhanced in further studies.

CONFLICT

There is no conflict of interest.

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